

“Influence of Visual Merchandising on Impulse Buying Behaviour of Customers in Sports Retail Outlet in Hubli City”

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ABSTRACT

Visual Merchandising is the practice in the retail industry for enhancing better experience of consumers and that can be done by developing floor plans and three-dimensional displays. An impulse purchase is an unplanned decision to buy a product or service, made just before a purchase, one who tends to make such purchases is referred to as an impulse purchaser or buyer. The intention of practicing visual merchandising is aimed at bring customers to the store and earn profits. The main purpose of this research paper is to study the most influential element of visual merchandising in impulse buying behaviour of customer in Sports Retail Outlet in Hubli City. The factors considered for the study are Window Display, Floor Merchandising, Mannequin Display and Promotional Signage. A questionnaire was administered and 150 responses were collected during the study. The data collected is analysed using Factor Analysis and Regression in SPSS. The researcher found that Promotional Signage and In-store Mannequin are the major influential factors in the selected element of the visual merchandising. It was also found from the study that the Influence of Promotion likes special signs and Signage like sale-signs were significantly associated with impulse buying behaviour.

Keywords: Visual Merchandising, Impulse buying behaviour, Window Display, Promotional Signage, Floor Merchandising and Mannequin Display

1. INTRODUCTION

Retail industry has caught lot of attention in the past one decade and it the fastest growing industry in India. It is expected that the industry is going to reach 1.1 trillion i.e. 60 Percent by the end of 2020. India is the fifth largest retail destination globally. The per capital retail store availability is highest in our country when compared to others. The Indian retail sector is not just growing and expanding in the major and metro cities, but it is having exponential growth in the Tier- II and Tier-III cities. Urbanisation, changing consumer tastes and preferences, changing demographic profile, economic growth, increasing disposable incomes and others are the factors driving to the growth of the retail market in India. It has been a shopping revolution in terms of format and consumer buying behaviour in India. Retail industry is witnessing a revolution as from shopping centres to multi-storied malls to huge complexes, entertainment and food all under one roof to new format markets like departmental, supermarkets and Hypermarkets have made their way to market. As there is rise in demand the consumers are getting more brands conscious. Indian retail market is changing due to dynamic demand

happening where increase in urbanisation is increasing purchasing power of customers, so there is ample of opportunities in the industry but there will challenges to be faced. Indian consumer market is likely to grow four times by 2025 (Neha P Mehta and Pawan K. Chugan, 2013). Recent days Retail industry has been in decline due to customers have moved to online purchase. This is the reason why it is important to incorporate Visual Merchandising strategies to improve the footprint of customers to the store.

According to K. Arun Prasad and Dr. S C Vetrivel (2016), Visual merchandizing is the presentation of a store and its merchandise in such a manner that will attract the attention of potential customers. It makes the store owner, sales manager and staff to meet their objectives or targets by increasing the average sales per customer. Visual Merchandising is been practiced since civilization i.e. when human started selling merchandising to customer. It was done when vendor started to think that his merchandise should look attractive and he started to arrange merchandise attractively. Visual Merchandising will encourage customers to get into the store which will improve the sales. How Visual Merchandising influence consumer Impulse buying behaviour is the problem to study? Impulse buying or purchase is the unplanned decision to buy a product was made just before a purchase. Visual Merchandising is about look and feel and the way the culture of the store is. If it is done properly than it will hence brand loyalty from customers. The importance of Visual Merchandising is makes product easier to locate, move product easier, promotes a positive experience and help explain new product in an easier way. Visual Merchandising presents an image of what the shopper can be while using the merchandising display (Dr. RahelaTabassum and Mr. Ishaq Khan, 2015). Once the customers walk in for the first time to the store it is very important that the customer is very satisfied with the first encounter so that customers can have repeated visit to the store. There are five elements which should be implicated those are Colour, Landscaping, Texture, Communication and Décor. Some key factors of Visual Merchandising are Window Display, Floor Merchandising, Mannequin Display and Signage.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The importance of store presentation is discussed by K. Arun Prasad and Dr. SC Vetrivel (2016), to understand the visual merchandising and its impact on consumer buying behaviour. The study emphasizes a lot on window displays; fixture, signage, mannequin, colours and lighting were significantly associated with consumer buying behaviour. Tolls used for analysed were Reliability analysis, Factor analysis and Multiple Regressions. It was observed that promotional signage play an important role in establishing a store image. .The study draws up a conclusion by emphasizing mannequin plays a great role giving customers an idea of what are the latest trends and the visual appearance of the merchandise. The study conducted by Rasa Gudonaviciene and Sonata Alijosience (2015), speaks us about visual merchandising elements. The two variables used in this study were window display and in-store design. The research was conducted applying a quantitative method for data collection of a survey; tool used in the survey was Standard deviation. The research states that window displays and in-store design - make the highest impact on impulse buying. Promotional signage and store atmosphere did significantly lead to customers' impulse buying behaviour. The results suggested that variables promotional signage and store atmosphere and customers impulse buying behaviour are correlated.

Khurram L. Bhatti and Seemab Latif (2013), explore to identify the association among consumer impulsive buying and visual merchandising on buying behaviour of customers in stores. Visual merchandising aims at introducing the product in style and with colour it educates the customers to make them take purchase decisions quick. The purpose of study is to identify the association between consumer impulsive buying and visual merchandising on buying behaviour of customers in stores. There were four hypothesis window display, forum display, floor merchandising and shop brand name. The Hypothesis ARE tested for regression analysis by using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. The results showed that there is significant association between window display, forum display, floor merchandising and shop brand name with consumer impulse buying behaviour.

The Importance of visual merchandising is discussed in vivid terms by Neha P. Mehta and Pawan K. Chugan (2013); the study is aimed to find out impact of various dimensions of visual merchandising on impulse buying behaviour of the customers. Four dimensions of visual merchandising those were window display, in-store form/mannequin in display, floor merchandising and promotional signage were studied and its impact on impulse buying behaviour is found out. They observed that window display is the first touch point of store with the customers. Hence, Window Display should be very attractive which enables to generate impulse buying and increase sales. Promotional signage and Floor display will enhance the experience of the store, so need to show a great floor display and signage should be visible clearly. Even though, in-store form/mannequin display did not significantly lead to customers' impulse buying behaviour. The study draws up conclusion that visual merchandising is important for strategic marketing decisions to increase the sales of the stores.

Dr. Rahela Tabassum and Mr. Ishaq Khan (2015), points out that in order to grab the attention of the customer's buying decision retail businesses must focus on visual merchandising. Visual Merchandising is not just about presenting the merchandise in an attractive manner but it also encourages impulse buying by the customers. This group gives lot of importance to Design, Layout, Window Displays, Mannequin, Music played and colour of products at the store and also gives lot of importance to styling the products at the store. The report highlights that the retail store managers need to focus more, on the driving features of sales, these features help the customer as well as the retail store in meeting their needs.

Ajith K. Thomas, Reni Louise and Vipinkumar VP (2018), studied in depth using its sample customers to find the impact of their buying behaviour. The research was of a descriptive in nature and helped to develop the concept. A structured questionnaire was used to obtain information and to assess the impact of visual merchandising, on impulse buying behaviour of customers. A random sampling technique was used in the study and care was taken that the respondents were as diversified as possible. To draw conclusions easily, the data was converted into Scatter diagrams. It was found out that impulse buying accounts for substantial sales across a broad range of product categories in the stores. Since impulse buying is a pervasive aspect of consumer's behaviours. It has been found that all the four visual merchandizing factors affect the impulse buying behaviour, but the effect of Promotional offerings at the entrance is comparatively very high. A greater importance should be given to visual merchandizing factors by retailers for differentiating itself from the competitors.

Dr. M. Mangala Gowri (2015) discussed that Impulse buying is a sudden and immediate purchase with no pre-shopping intentions either to buy the specific product or to fulfil a specific buying task. This study tried to explain to explain the relationship between customers' impulse buying behaviour based on various visual merchandising techniques and their relationship. Window display, in-store form/mannequin display, floor merchandising, and promotional signage are the most important factors which significantly generates interest for customers in impulse buying. The study outlines that impulse buying had been influenced based on the various visual merchandising practices such as in-store form / mannequin display and promotional signage. Window display, in-store form/mannequin display, floor merchandising, and promotional signage are the most important factors which significantly generates interest for customers in impulse buying.

RESEARCH GAPS

- Studies with respect to sports retail has not be done in North-Karnataka.
- No study has been done on Hubli location.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

PRIMARY OBJECTIVE

“Influence of Visual Merchandising on Impulse Buying Behaviour of Customers at Sports Retail Outlet in Hubli City”

SECONDARY OBJECTIVES

- To study how visual merchandising influence on impulse buying behaviour of customers.
- To ascertain the factors of visual merchandising that influences people to purchase in the store.
- To analyse the highly influential visual merchandising factor on consumer buying behaviour in Sports Retail Outlet in Hubli City.

DATA COLLECTION

Questionnaire was designed for the purpose of collecting data. A total of 150 respondents were considered for the study. The researcher has adopted the convenient sampling method for his study. Likert scale has been adapted to measure the “the study the influence of visual merchandising on consumer buying behaviour”. Five point Likert scale has been used for the study.

SAMPLE SIZE

A sample of 150 customers has been taken in order to carry out the study in Sports Retail Outlet in Hubli City.

SAMPLE ELEMENTS

The sample elements will consist of people who visit and shop from Sports Retail Outlet in Hubli City.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INFERENCE

TABLE NO 1
KMO AND BARTLETT'S TEST

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.703
Approx. Chi-Square	282.672
	91
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity df	.000

INFERENCE

The KMO measure of sampling adequacy test gives 0.703 showing the sufficiently of data to employ factor analysis. The Bartlett's test of Sphericity for the appropriateness of factor analysis is satisfactory, as the chi-square value is calculated as 282.672 at a degree of freedom 91 and with p value within the threshold limit ($p < 0.001$). Since the estimated value of chi-square is very high and the result is significant, factor analysis is appropriate for the present data set.

TABLE NO 2
TOTAL VARIANCE EXPLAINED

COMPONENT	INITIAL EIGENVALUES			EXTRACTION SUMS OF SQUARED LOADINGS			ROTATION SUMS OF SQUARED LOADINGS			EXTRACTION
	TOTAL	% OF VARIANCE	CUMULATIVE %	TOTAL	% OF VARIANCE	CUMULATIVE %	TOTAL	% OF VARIANCE	CUMULATIVE %	
1	3.037	21.692	21.692	3.037	21.692	21.692	2.006	14.328	14.328	.638
2	1.357	9.689	31.382	1.357	9.689	31.382	1.685	12.038	26.366	.590
3	1.242	8.872	40.254	1.242	8.872	40.254	1.403	10.023	36.389	.477
4	1.179	8.421	48.675	1.179	8.421	48.675	1.348	9.630	46.019	.733
5	1.081	7.722	56.397	1.081	7.722	56.397	1.258	8.987	55.006	.632
6	1.026	7.326	63.722	1.026	7.326	63.722	1.220	8.717	63.722	.635
7	.854	6.099	69.822							.579
8	.829	5.919	75.741							.705
9	.737	5.267	81.008							.679
10	.663	4.735	85.742							.501
11	.581	4.153	89.896							.712
12	.520	3.717	93.612							.783
13	.473	3.375	96.987							.599
14	.422	3.013	100.00							.659

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

TABLE NO 3
ROTATED COMPONENT MATRIX

	COMPONENT					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Unintended	.774					
Special Signs	.722					
Complicated	.550					
Looking		.815				
Rely SD New		.552				
Design In store		.542				
Interesting WD Eye			.791			
Catching Whole				.807		
Section Isle				.724		
Promotional Offer					.803	
Sale Signs						.870
Pass by						
% of Variance	21.692	9.689	8.872	8.421	7.722	7.326
Total	3.037	1.357	1.242	1.179	1.081	1.026

INFERENCE

The above table 3 and 4 stand for Total Variance explained and Rotated Component Matrix respectively. The principal component analysis approach, using varimax rotation, reduced the explanatory variables in to 6 major factors based on the 11 values greater than 0.50. The criterion of factor loading was based on the absolute value of co-efficient in the Rotated Component Matrix. Each factor was composed of specific explanatory variables that loaded more than 0.50 on the factor. In the co-efficient display format option co-efficient with values less than 0.50 were suppressed. The variables were sorted by size under factor based on the absolute values of their loadings. The total variance explained by the factor analysis is calculated at 63.722. Of these factors Influence of Promotional Signage has the maximum factors (4), Influence on In-Store/ Mannequin Display has the second maximum (3) factors, Influence of Window Display and Floor Merchandising has two factors (2) each factors loading under each component.

**TABLE NO 4
MODEL SUMMARY**

MODEL	R	R SQUARE	ADJUSTED R SQUARE	STD. ERROR OF THE ESTIMATE
1	.618 ^a	.381	.355	2.23044

INFERENCE

Predictors: (Constant), Signage, Offer, Display, Mannequin, Floor, Promotion

This table (5) provides the R and R² values. The R value represents the simple correlation and is 0.618 (the “R” Column), which indicates a high degree of correlation. The R² value (the “R²” Column), which indicates how much of the total variation in the dependent variable can be explained by the independent variable. In this case, 38.1% can be explained which is good one.

**TABLE NO 5
ANOVA**

MODEL	SUM OF SQUARES	DF	MEAN SQUARE	F	SIG.
Regression	438.566	6	73.094	14.693	.000 ^b
Residual	711.407	143	4.975		
Total	1149.973	149			

- Dependent Variable: Impulse
- Predictors: (Constant), Signage, Offer, Display, Mannequin, Floor, Promotion

INFERENCE

The table (6) indicates that the regression model predicts the dependent variable significantly well. How do we know this? Look at the “Regression” row and go the “Sig” column. This indicates the statistical significance of the regression model. Here, p<0.000, which is less than 0.05, and indicates that overall the regression model statistically significantly predicts the outcome variable (i.e. it is good fit for the data).

**TABLE NO 6
COEFFICIENTS**

MODEL	UNSTANDARDIZED COEFFICIENTS		STANDARDIZED COEFFICIENTS	T	SIG.
	B	STD. ERROR	BETA		
(Constant) Mannequin Display Promotion Offer Floor Signage	4.760	2.040		2.333	.021
	.039	.118	.023	.328	.744
	.405	.283	.096	1.428	.156
	.718	.109	.466	6.560	.000
	.137	.072	.127	1.903	.059
	-.126	.168	-.053	-.750	.454
	1.210	.272	.299	4.443	.000

Dependent Variable: Impulse

$$\text{Impulse Buying Behaviour} = 4.760 + 0.39 * \text{Mannequin} + .0405 * \text{Display} + 0.718 * \text{Promotion} + 0.137 * \text{Offer} - 0.126 * \text{Floor} + 1.210 * \text{Signage}$$

INFERENCE

From the table (7) the predicator Mannequin: B= 0.039, T= 0.328, P= 0.744 is statically insignificant; Display: B= 0.405, T= 1.428, P= 0.156 is statically insignificant; Promotion: B= 0.718, T= 6.560, P= 0.000 statically significant; Offer: B = 0.137, T= 1.903, P= 0.059 is statically insignificant; Floor: P= -0.126, T= -0.750, P= 0.454 is not statically insignificant; Signage: B= 1.210, T= 4.443, P= 0.000 is statically significant.

4. CONCLUSION

The study investigated some factors that influence impulse buying behaviour as there is no pre-purchase decision taken. The main purpose was to identify the influence of Visual Merchandising on impulse buying behaviour of customers in Decathlon, Hubli. This study was an attempt to find out the relationship between visual merchandising and the impulse decision on buying or purchase. The study was also done to find out the relationship between one variable to another variable i.e. relationship between dependent variable to independent. Since the R² value is the indication of the total variation in the dependent variable and the results shows good one. The results showed that the most influential factors are Influence of Promotional Signage and Influence of in-store-Mannequin and in terms of relationship Signage and Promotion are statically significant. Even though the results of Display, Mannequin, Offer and Floor are not statically significant but impulse buying behaviour variable are correlated so the results still suggest that the variables are correlated with impulse buying behaviour. As the most influential factors are Promotional Signage and Mannequin so company must clearly show the differentiation of signage board of with offers an without offers and Mannequin should be kept so the apparels can be clearly visible for the customers.

When consumers are exposed to visual merchandise then they tend to make purchase based on impulse decisions. This suggests that visual merchandising practices which provoke the consumers to make unplanned purchase decision about entering the store which influence impulse consumer buying behaviour. The sporting apparels and equipment's can be impulse purchase so visual merchandise will play impact role in the purchase decision. The variables which are not statistically significant marketers must make necessary work on that so that the sales of the store can increase. Merchandise in the store should be neatly arranged and there should not be any shabby which gives negative impact for the customers. Hence, marketers should adopt all the criteria which will enhance the store with more number of footprints and increase the impulse purchase.

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